

THE CONSTRUCTION OF THE FEMALE PROTAGONIST IN *PI-WII*, BY CYNTHIA PINHEIRO

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ABSTRACT

This intends researches to reflect on the fictional construction of the character Pi-wii, the female protagonist of the book entitled *Pi-wii* (2022), written by Cynthia Pinheiro. The book tells the story of five Cambodian children, motherless and whose parent is a cruel and violent man, capable of carrying out atrocities, torture and abuse (psychological and sexual) against his five children. Pi-wii is a child who had to assume the responsibilities of being a woman early and from a very young age began to experience extreme poverty and violence to which she was subjected by her parent. From the analysis of the constitution of the character's trajectory, we seek to relate the construction of her fictional character with the social conditions of women in the 21st century, as well as the similarities to so many others in third world countries. Therefore, the methodology used to carry out this research is embodied in the literature review, supported by the Feminist Critical Theory. We also resort to the studies of Duarte (1997), Xavier (1996), Coelho (1993), Schmidt (2012), Candido (2011), among others. Based on the critical reading and the analyzes carried out, we perceive in Cynthia Pinheiro textual universe that the reader does not leave intact, since his horizon of expectations, when incorporated into the horizon

offered by the novel, provides new perspectives on the literature of contemporary female authorship, of the female body, of resistance to patriarchal systems and violent and human rights environments.

Keywords: Literature by female authorship. Character. Pi-wii. Cynthia Pinheiro.

INTRODUCTION

When we enter into a discussion about the literature of female authorship produced in the context of postmodernity - here we define it as an extensive ideological concept, which encompasses the industrial and economic infrastructure and the globalization of the world, from the 1960s to the present day -, especially with regard to ruptures with what was already established and proposed by the tradition of literary production in Brazil, it becomes, like this research, essential to highlight some significant itineraries that the woman-writer has trodden to free herself from erasure and the silencing of their scriptures, as well as promoting anti-patriarchal representations and literary discourses.

For this, this research intends to reflect on the fictional construction of the character Pi-wii, the female protagonist of the book entitled *Pi-wii* (2022), written by Cynthia Pinheiro. The book under review tells the story of five children from Cambodia, a Southeast Asian nation, motherless and whose parent is a cruel and violent man, capable of carrying out atrocities, torture and abuse (psychological and sexual) against his five children. Pi-wii, in turn, is a child who had to assume the responsibilities of being a woman at an early age and from a very young age began to experience extreme poverty and violence to which she was subjected.

Cynthia Pinheiro was born and raised in Montes Claros, Minas Gerais, but has an agreed birth certificate in Taiobeiras - MG. Graduated in Music from the State University of Montes Claros, with a postgraduate degree in Art Education; she has worked for 22 years at the Lorenzo Fernandez State Conservatory of Music (Celf), where she teaches singing and music history. He has published seven books, including poetry for children and adults, opera, short stories, chronicles and reflections. He has also written two books as *a ghostwriter* (a biography and a book on hypnosis). And, in 2022, he published his first novel: *Pi-wii*.

Our reflections are, here, undertaken from concepts undertaken by Feminist Critical Theory, which emphasize issues related, on the one hand, to sociological aspects, systematized from the representation of gender relations and the construction of female identities, as well as embodied in the literature review, with the aim of systematizing all existing information on a given phenomenon in an impartial and/or complete manner. We also resorted to the studies of

Constância Lima Duarte (1997), Elódia Xavier (1996), Nelly Novaes Coelho (1993), Rita Terezinha Schimdt (2012), Antonio Candido (2011), among others.

In summary, based on the critical reading and analysis carried out, we perceive in the textual universe and, above all, Cyntia Pinheiro's contemporary universe, that the reader does not leave intact, since his horizon of expectations, when incorporating himself to the horizon offered by the novel, provides new perspectives on female-authored literature, the female body, resistance to patriarchal systems and violent environments, and human rights.

Literature written by women throughout history

We know that female-authored literature has its own characteristics and throughout history we can reiterate that it is parallel to the culture of patriarchy²⁹; in which women were generally involved in domestic work and with concerns for the family. In this sense, we understand that there was an erasure of female writing, with little importance being given to their literature in previous centuries, an aspect in which it is related to the literary canon.

According to Antonio Candido (2000), in his book *Formation of Brazilian Literature*: decisive moments, the literary canon comprises a set of works considered as hegemonic models of a given literary period, style or culture; as a rule, precept or norm, to be followed by male and female writers. For example, *Dom Casmurro* (1889), by Machado de Assis, or even *Grande sertão: veredas* (1956), by Guimarães Rosa, can be understood as canon works of Brazilian literature.

From such considerations, we can infer that in the most intimate part of the canon, “classic” texts are (and were) privileged, and texts that do not fit their time and pre-established criteria are ignored. This is because, for Candido (2000), literary historiography tends to establish oligarchic predilections, since the first half of the 19th century, when authors wrote sketches, florilegiums, editions of works, which were influenced by romantic-European criticism, which aimed to of a national literature.

In other words, all postulations that deviate from the canon configurations, such as that of an ethnic minority, of gender, of a periphery, of a non-dominant social class, tend to be excluded, as they are diminished in terms of their capacity to formulate contents that reinforce

²⁹ According to Barbano and Cruz (2015), the aforementioned term can be understood as a social construction in which men maintain primary power and predominate in roles of political leadership, moral authority, social privilege and control of properties. In the family domain, the father maintains authority over women and children.

hegemonic values. The canon, therefore, is wrapped in a historical-social context and by games of interest and power. (CANDIDO, 2000).

In this perspective, the article “The issue of the canon”, by Zahidé Muzart (1995), addresses that female literature had an evident disappearance in terms of literature in general. Muzart (1995) also reports that from the 20th century new women scholars could emerge who would rescue the writing of women who were erased. As an example, we highlight Lúcia Miguel Pereira (1901-1959), a woman who had little knowledge as a writer, but known as an essayist and biographer of Machado de Assis; or even Maria Firmina dos Reis (1822-1917), writer from Maranhão, black, teacher in times of enslavement³⁰; author of the novel *Úrsula* (1859), one of the first female-authored narratives to be published in Brazil.

To emphasize this need to rescue the writing of these women erased over time, Muzart says: “[...] in addition to the rescue, the publication of the texts, it is necessary to revive these women by bringing their texts back to the readers, criticizing them, contextualizing them, comparing them, among themselves or with male writers, contributing to put them back in their place in History” (MUZART, 1995, p. 90).

It becomes pertinent, then, to study female writers who have disappeared from literature, especially Brazilian female authors. This is because, according to Margareth Rago (1995), in her article “Women in Brazilian historiography”, this reflection “[...] becomes all the more necessary, the more we realize that History does not narrate the past, but constructs a discourse about it, bringing both the look and the very subjectivity of the one who cuts and narrates, in his own way, the matter of history” (RAGO, 1995, p. 81).

In line with the three issues of the non-place of women in literary historiography, based on Rago's studies (1995), the author points out the marks of cultural history and the category of gender, that is, the way of building history and rescue female participation; questions concerning the intentionality of engaging in moral conduct and preserving a *status quo* still present in the late nineteenth century and even today (RAGO, 1995).

As we enter into a discussion about Brazilian female authorship literature produced in the context of postmodernity, we also seek to reflect on the participation of women in literary

³⁰ We chose to use the noun “enslavement” with the noun “slavery”. This is because the first, in our understanding, comprises the act or effect of enslaving, and the second, in turn, the state or condition of a slave; Man's subjection regime and use of his strength, exploited for economic purposes, as private property. Thus, the first term takes shape and life in the present time, that is, it appears as a scar that still insists on pulsating and, mainly, as a memory for those bodies that lived and survived the system of slavery not only in Brazilian territory, but also from the overall design.

historiography and the debates in vogue collaborate for expansions in relation to the theme and for the deconstruction of a male identity in supremacy.

And in contemporary times, we highlight the emergence of new women in literature, such as the writer Conceição Evaristo. Among his works are the novels *Ponciá Vicêncio* (2003) and *Becos da Memória* (2006) , and the poetry book *Poemas da lembrança and other movements* (2006) . In addition, Conceição Evaristo has published three collections of short stories: *Olhos d'água* (2006) , *Stories of light mistakes and similarities* (2006) and *Insubmissas tears of women* (2011) .

Bárbara Araújo Machado (2014), in her dissertation entitled “Recording is necessary: Conceição Evaristo and the black intelligentsia in the context of the contemporary Brazilian black movement (1982-2008)”, says that the writer tells much of her story in her works, a since Evaristo coined a term for his literature, committed to the condition of a black woman in a society marked by diverse prejudices: writing. For the author, the term points to a double dimension: it is life that is written in the experience and intimacy of each person, of each individual who lives in society, just as each one writes the world they face (MACHADO, 2014).

In view of this, it becomes possible to rescue Brazilian female writers, as mentioned by Muzart (1995), given that it is necessary to revive their names, after so many centuries forgotten, systematically ignored and on the margins of history, and which, at present, begin to occupy the space that belongs to them in the arts, literature, politics and society.

For Constância Lima Duarte (2022), in a recent organization of articles written by national researchers, the *Memorial do memoricide* : female writers forgotten by history, while “[...] men dominated the public space, women remained confined to their homes, illiterate, taking care only of tasks related to the family and submitted to a patriarchal order that established their inferiority” (DUARTE, 2022, p. 15). However, some young women escaped this limited vicious circle and published poems, novels, essays and even plays, but they are still being erased by the canon.

Still according to Duarte (2022), along with these situations that were (and still are) imposed on women, diversity exists; the entries contain information about the life and work of each writer, in addition to research sources that give clues to those who want to expand their study.

Following the context of new names in the literature, Cyntia Pinheiro's rubric and physiology appear. It took her a while, even with eight books published, to call herself a “writer”

and no longer a “writer”³¹. Currently a writer, she writes. Write to be read. There is, therefore, in her first novel, creativity and originality – traits and voices of her predecessors, the silenced ones, but which are remembered throughout our discussions.

Initially, we emphasize that, despite the initial aversion to envisioning what is set scene by scene by the author, through her multifaceted narrators, in the first person, therefore, intrinsic characters of the story, that this feeling happens after the author creates the “man”, a being without name and identity, who cannot be easily displaced in terms of cruelty. The “man” does not kill his victims – his offspring and all those around him – he wants to torture them into pieces, broken and alive, for his use and pleasure.

When Cyntia Pinheiro deals with time, an element of construction of the narration and present in chronological or psychological texts, she behaves with absolute knowledge about all things, the scenarios (historical-geographical), the habits and customs (before and after. present time) of Cambodia. It takes the voice of several of two characters, which results in the narrative's point of view of those who have the word. This resource, polyphony, characteristic of texts in which several voices are present, in other words, does not confuse the reader who, from an immediate understanding, knows who is telling their life story, resistance, overcoming the patriarchal and violent system. that awaits them, day after day.

Given these considerations, we reiterate that the novel *Pi-wii*, by Cyntia Pinheiro, is an invitation to social reflection and, of course, to a critical reading of society. In addition, her characters, who blend between reality and fiction, appear in her book as Ulysses, one of the main heroes of Greek literature, protagonist of the epic poems *Iliad* and *Odyssey*, by Homer. Hero, like *Pi-wii*, for its intelligence to live the adventures and challenges that cross its paths.

The protagonist *Pi-wii* in the literature of Cyntia Pinheiro

The novel *Pi-wii* is named after the protagonist of the book. The character *Pi-wii*, 12 years old, is a child from a rural village in the extreme northeast of Cambodia, in 1985. She is motherless and the older sister of five: Kol-ha is ten years old, Sami is eight, Derehpan is six and Nhean is four, and has become the mother figure of the younger siblings since their mother died during the birth of the last child. The birth of the latter was the trigger: “[...] that was when the man [the father] went crazy” (PINHEIRO, 2022, p. 21, emphasis added).

³¹ The term “writer”, articulated here by both researchers, refers to those people who write not to be read, but to be read. Read themselves. A view of themselves.

Initially, when we mention the question of the maternal figure imposed by the threads that weave the destiny of life, this data in the novel by Cyntia Pinheiro invites us to an individual and collective reflection on and how each being lives in society, being man or woman, has exercised their functions related to maternity and paternity and what reflections the understanding and experiences of these new configurations have on the exercise of their respective functions today. Therefore, we can associate Pi-wii's early mothering with the sensitivity and acceptance of the "other", since she, no longer inhabiting her body, inhabits five others; one inhabits, then, behaviors, functions, care, responsibilities and nuances of the maternal seal and the family, social or cultural role of a mother.

From that first presentation of the character, there is something that is confronted with the past: the primordial divinity since the dawn of the History of Humanity. In Greek mythology, Pi-wii can be understood as Mother Earth, Gaia, link and generative potentiality; associated with multiple aspects of life, from breeding and procreation, to Nature and working the land, to family and the protection of children (CHEVALIER; GHEERBRANT, 1998).

This analysis can be understood from the following excerpts:

[...] the man's jealousy ensured that I could dedicate myself more to my brothers and to taking care of them, if it weren't like that, I would have to work in the rice field from a very early age and I preferred to take care of my wards, feeding them, guiding and protecting them. [...] I'm good at caring. I know the ointments that the bush offers, nobody taught me, I just know. [...] The bush is indeed wise, it is silent in reverence to the wind that blows, it lets the wind sing and perfume the world, and by the smell that the wind carries I know how to make remedies for all the pains of my brothers' bodies (PINHEIRO, 2022, p. 21-22).

Given the above, we can see that the look and the way the character lives is the result of a complex accumulation of practices, techniques and meanings. These three elements constitute not only the subjective way in which she sees, the way she inserts herself and deals with the world, but also the knowledge available in her historical moment to which she is placed. From this angle, for Pi-wii, getting to know the traditional knowledge that preceded modern knowledge is a way of going through the construction of the reality that had been imposed on him and, thus, appropriating the history of the people themselves.

In the course of the novel, the plot delivers a set of successive events experienced by the characters in specific space and time. From it, it becomes possible to know Cyntia Pinheiro's view of Cambodia: a country devastated by a recent Civil War, which ended around 1979, however, Cambodians only returned to live in "relative peace" after the years 90. According to the author, however, the imagined Cambodia is a "[...] commonplace, such a story could take

place anywhere on the planet, and who said it didn't happen anyway? Are there no other girls out there as suffering as our protagonist?" (PINHEIRO, 2022, p. 15).

Still according to the author, the emergence and creation of *Pi-wii* happened after a dream, as described in the "Presentation" of the novel, in which

[...] five children ran away from home, from the persecution of a cruel and mentally damaged parent. When writing the first word on the computer screen, the whole story emerged in a kind of catharsis, it took two days of writing that immediately yielded more than two hundred pages. But something was missing. What was missing was diving into their lives, what was missing was getting to know this mysterious place for me, Cambodia. Why Cambodia? And off I went to research, read, watch, talk about it and delve deeper into the lives of those children. (PINHEIRO, 2022, p. 15-16).

Seeking to deepen what she had already written, Cyntia Pinheiro began to “[...] think like those children, to walk with their legs, to live their lives, I immersed myself so deeply in their stories that I was often moved by my writing itself. It was too painful to feel their pain, but they were in me” (PINHEIRO, 2022, p. 16); Another significant point for the author was realizing that those children inhabited her from dawn until the early hours of the morning: “They generously populated my dreams, including me in their personal tragedies, revealing to me their pain and their secrets and I needed to write about them. that” (PINHEIRO, 2022, p. 16).

As explained by Beth Brait (1987), in her book *A personage*, the process of creating a fictional human figure created by an author – freely depending on whether it is intended for fiction or not – requires planning and responsibility from those who will develop the project. This is because, for Cyntia Pinheiro, it is necessary to give it a purpose and also make the public identify with its weaknesses and goals. This score is raised by the author herself not being able to distinguish to what extent *Pi-wii* is an invented girl, or the novel is something created by her, as she is the representation of so many girls mistreated by life (PINHEIRO, 2022).

Pi-wii, according to the threads that weave the narrative, is an intelligent girl and begins her trajectory outside of school, of society. She has a talent for caring for the health of her brothers, based on her knowledge of what her past generation left her as a legacy of blood: the tradition of using home remedies to cure common ailments such as colds, flu and ailments . digestives ; the wounds and traumas caused by “man”.

Pi-wii has in its fictional construction the representation of literary texts written by women in recent years (the 1990s onwards), as asserted by Lúcia Osana Zolin (2011), based on her article *The construction of the female character in contemporary Brazilian literature (re)written by women*, for a new look at female bodies in a system of subordination, aggression,

violence, abuse and, above all, refusal of ideologies similar to patriarchy. In addition, it points to a tendency to engage the reader and he, in turn, to be moved by the (in)visible existence of those five Cambodian children, similar to so many others in countries considered as “third world”, rooted in the ordeal of obscurity, in the erasure of their voices. (ZOLIN, 2011).

In its first chapter, Pinheiro (2022) through its narrator-character initiates the first imagery recreation of *Pi-wii*, in first person, giving the narrative the scars that shaped his body, his personality, his reception to the eyes of third parties. Scars exposed like trophies caused by her progenitor, which any human being is incapable of bearing and she was driven over the last four years:

I have cracked upper lips, not hare, cracked by paternal violence. The man thought that, after my mother died, I had to be his wife and I ended up being the same, many times. The man shaved my hair with a blunt blade, said he didn't want any male looking at me, that I'm slovenly enough with my mouth broken, [...] Being a woman as a child is not a good thing. It's out of order, out of place. There is no nirvana in that kind of precocity, only pain and suffering. As his wife, I am also the mother of my brothers and I can't bear to see what that man does to them. [...] Sami is a girl like me, and I suspect that the man has already made her a woman too. [...] She is sad. [...] because he no longer has the eyes of a child. (PINHEIRO, 2022, p. 21).

In light of the above, it becomes possible to understand that a literary work, especially a novel, such as *Pi-wii*, is only fully realized as a paper being when it communicates to readers “[...] the impression of the most legitimate existential truth”, this through “[...] a fictitious being” (CANDIDO, 2011, p. 55). In other words, the aforementioned author expresses that literary works are only realized when they excel in the genesis of verisimilitude, that is, when they try to convince the reader, through the construction of their characters, that everything written in them is likely to be true, in a “[...] certain type of relationship between the living being and the fictitious being” (CANDIDO, 2011, p. 55).

In this way, the presentation of the character by herself, on each page, seeks to expose “life” as it develops, capturing the character’s existence in the decisive moments of her existence, or at least in the moments recorded in her memory as instants. decisive, intrinsic to the constitution of his being.

Still according to the passage, one can note in *Pi-wii*'s record the evils of premature maturation and stolen innocence: of mildness and systematic violence against his body and his identity. By mentioning her father as a “man”, in the background, the opposite of what she expected from him is evidenced, the father figure of a family, or the genitor of a person. and, yes, a cruel being, capable of atrocities and seeing his daughter as his, as his new woman.

The cracked upper lips, the cut hair, the pain and suffering carry an injured, harassed, flagellated image. In this way, the novel inevitably establishes a parallel with the real world and, consequently, its protagonist, a parallel with the people who live in it. Thus, as Candido (2011) explains, the physical record of Pi-wii becomes even more credible when it carries within itself the complexity or psychological density of the people who are part of reality.

Still according to the author, as it happens to human beings, in psychological terms, it is possible to make the characters of books more complex, more mysterious, more difficult to unravel, more unexpected and, consequently, more intriguing and more convincing for readers (CANDIDO , 2011).

Returning to the novel, the story recounts moments of sexual, physical, psychological violence and other negligence experienced by Pi-wii and his brothers. Thus, the author gives voice to all the brothers and with that we can see through the eyes of different characters, except Nhean, who is the youngest child, since his life is ended by a high fever that has not been treated. However, the novel also inserts other characters that contribute to the narrative.

The figures from other countries that make up the scenario of Pi-wii's life, offer the reader, its target audience, a valuable representative of the female thinking world, this is due to the evidence provided by the text and its readability through various methods . One of them is the figure of a doctor, whose Non-Governmental Organization (NGO) is not entirely fictional, but present in that country, where many units provide help to the population (PINHEIRO, 2022).

Another significant point for the construction of the character is knowing that after a minor material achievement, but glorious for her and her siblings, the adoption, they would embark for “picturesque England”, due to the documentation bureaucracy, since there was no “[. .] no origin, no record, no surname” (PINHEIRO, 2022, p. 193). But the doctor took care of their case, providing everything necessary for the adoption to be successful.

Pi-wii was adopted by Katherine Johnson and her husband Philip Johnson. They didn't have children, fully capable of having them, but opted for adoption, since they understood that there were many children in the third world country who needed a family. “Upon seeing me, the couple showed no revulsion or alarm at my appearance. They hugged me affectionately” (PINHEIRO, 2022, p. 193).

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

Pi-wii, by *Cyntia Pinheiro* as the object of our reflections, we seek to demonstrate the construction of its protagonist-character, in addition to relating the construction of its fictional character to the social conditions faced by women in the 21st century, as well as the similarities to so many others in third world countries. Also, make your name visible and point out the directions of your trajectory, emphasizing, consequently, the marks of your book in the present time and your character as a reflection of contemporary reality.

Some themes found in the literary work are considered of great impact and lead us to think and reflect on aspects of Human Rights. Even before the narrative, the author points out that the book contains excerpts that can trigger mental triggers, as it tells stories of rape and violence against children.

Pi-wii readers will certainly not be as resilient as she is, they will not come out of this plunge unscathed, because *Cyntia Pinheiro's* sensitivity, her ability to see the world and grasp the complexity of the beings she inhabits in her movements are realized in verbal articulation. In other words, the character managed to build a new world, even though she was predestined to failure and the scars of the past still pulsate on her skin. Reading provokes, in a way, a character of resilience and compassion.

There is no way to get to know the *Pi-wii* and go back to being the same, you have to reflect and transform yourself so that the world becomes a better place. Therefore, reading her novel is reading the story of women who live in the background, not having their human rights guaranteed, being considered apart from the public sphere.

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